

Article name	Author(s)	Year	Food/ drink type
Young consumers' purchase intention toward organic food: exploring the role of mindfulness	Tewari et al.	2022	organic food
Young consumers' purchase behaviour of sustainably-labelled food products. What is the role of scepticism?	Rossi & Rivetto	2023	sustainably labelled food
"Young and Green" a Study of Consumers' Perceptions and Reported Purchasing Behaviour towards Organic Food in Poland and the United Kingdom	Kowalska et al.	2021	organic food products
Willingness of Iranian young adults to eat organic foods: Application of the Health Belief Model	Yazdanpanah et al.	2015	organic food
Why do consumers buy organic food? Results from an S-O-R model	Liang & Lim	2021	organic food
When mindful consumption meets short food supply chains: Empirical evidence on how higher-level motivations influence consumers	Benos et al.	2022	Short Food Supply Chain (SFSC) foods

What Stirs Consumers to Purchase Carbon-Friendly Food? Investigating the Motivational and Emotional Aspects in Three Studies	Penz and Hofmann Penz and Hofmann	2021 ""	carbon-friendly food carbon-friendly food
study 3 What motivates Indian consumers' to buy organic food in an emerging market?	Jose et al.	2020	organic fruits and vegetables
What motivates German consumers to reduce their meat consumption? Identifying relevant beliefs	Seffen and Dohle	2023	meat
What motivates consumers to purchase organic food in an emerging market? An empirical study from Saudi Arabia	Mohammed	2021	organic food
What motivates consumers to buy organic foods? Results of an empirical study in the United States	Gundala and Singh	2021	organic food
What influences consumers to purchase organic food in developing countries?	Pacho	2020	organic food

What drives willingness to purchase and stated buying behavior toward organic food? A Stimuluse-Organisme-Behaviore-Consequence (SOBC) perspective	talwar et al.	2021	organic food
What drives organic food purchasing? - evidence from Croatia	Ham et al.	2018	organic food
What drives organic food consumption in Lebanon?	Tleis et al.	2019	organic food
What drives Malaysian consumers' organic food purchase intention? The role of moral norm, self-identity, environmental concern and price consciousness	Saleki et al.	2019	organic food
What drives attitude, purchase intention and consumer buying behavior toward organic food? A self-determination theory and theory of planned behavior perspective	Khan et al.	2022	organic food
What determines British consumers' motivation to buy sustainable seafood?	Honkanen and Young	2015	sustainable seafood

What determines a positive attitude towards natural food products? An expectancy theory approach	Talwar et al.	2021	natural food products
Values, Motives, and Organic Food Consumption in China: A Moderating Role of Perceived Uncertainty Values and Planned Behaviour of the Romanian Organic Food Consumer	Wei et al.	2022	organic food
Using theory of consumption values to predict organic food purchase intention: Role of health consciousness and eco-friendly LOHAS tendency	Fleseriu et al.	2020	organic fruits and vegetables
Urban Residents' Green Agro-Food Consumption: Perceived Risk, Decision Behaviors, and Policy Implications in China	Kose and Kircova	2021	organic food
Understanding the purchase intentions for organic vegetables across EU: a proposal to extend the TPB model	Xiao et al.	2023	green agro-food
	Loera et al.	2022	organic vegetables

Understanding the drivers of organic foods purchasing of millennials: Evidence from Brazil and Spain	Molinillo et al.	2020	organic foods
Understanding the consumption of plant-based meat alternatives and the role of health-related aspects. A study of the Italian market	Rizzo et al.	2023	plant-based meat alternatives (PBMA)
Understanding the Antecedents of Organic Food Consumption in Pakistan: Moderating Role of Food Neophobia	Akbar et al.	2019	organic food
Understanding organic food consumption: attitude as a mediator	Cabuk et al.	2014	organic food
Understanding organic food consumption in the European Union: the interaction between health and environmental consumer's goals	Valero-Gil et al.	2023	organic food
Understanding food pleasure in organic consumption: the moderating effects of trust within the theory of planned behavior	Cao et al.	2024	organic food
Understanding factors underlying actual consumption of organic food: The moderating effect of future orientation	Chekima et al.	2019	organic food

Underlying Motivations of Organic Food Purchase Intentions	Nasir and Karakaya	2014	organic food
Trust to Go Green: An Exploration of Consumer Intentions for Eco-friendly Convenience Food	Ricci et al.	2018	minimally processed vegetables labelled with integrated-pest-management standards
Towards More Sustainable Diets: Investigating Consumer Motivations towards the Purchase of Green Food	Chang et al.	2021	precooked plant-based foods (PCPBF)
Towards Environmentally Sustainable Diets: Consumer Attitudes and Purchase Intentions for Plant-Based Meat Alternatives in Taiwan	Chen	2022	plant-based meat
Toward acceptance of future foods: the role of trust and perception in consumption intentions of plant-based meat alternatives	Begho et al.	2022	plant-based meat alternatives (PBMA)
To combine or not to combine? Applying protection motivation theory and the theory of reasoned action to explain and predict intention to reduce meat consumption	Chen	2022	meat

The self-regulatory function of anticipated pride and guilt in a sustainable and healthy consumption context	Onwezen et al.	2014	organic food fair trade food products fruit
a	""	""	
b	""	""	
The role of trust in the relationship between consumers, producers and retailers of organic food: A sector-based approach	Ladwein and Romero	2021	organic food
The role of subjective norms in theory of planned behavior in the context of organic food consumption	Al-Swidi et al.	2014	organic food
The role of subjective norms in forming the intention to purchase green food	Ham et al.	2015	green food
The role of psychological food involvement in explaining the intention to reduce meat consumption	Castellini et al.	2023	meat
The Role of Green Self-Identity and Self-Congruity in Sustainable Food Consumption Behaviour	Gravelines et al.	2022	Sustainable Food Consumption

The role of food eating values and exploratory behaviour traits in predicting intention to consume organic foods: An extended planned behaviour approach	Sadiq et al.	2021	organic food
The role of environmentally conscious purchase behaviour and green scepticism in organic food consumption	Golob et al.	2018	environmentally friendly products; organic food
The role of environmental concern in purchasing decision on organic food and the link to greenwashing	Kocer et al.	2023	organic food
The role of consumers in transitions towards sustainable food consumption. The case of organic food in Norway	Vitterso and Tangeland	2015	organic food
The role of consciousness in sustainable food consumption: a cultural comparison	Ahn and Shamim	2023	organic food brands
The role of brand reputation in organic food consumption: A behavioral reasoning perspective	Ryan and Casidy	2018	organic breakfast cereal

The relationships between core values, food-specific future time perspective and sustainable food consumption	Olsen and Tuu	2021	sustainable food consumption
The modulation of sustainability knowledge and impulsivity traits on the consumption of foods of animal and plant origin in Italy and Turkey	Migliavada et al.	2022	plant-based foods (vegetables, pulses, tofu, nuts, fruits)
	'''	'''	plant-based foods (vegetables, pulses, tofu, nuts, fruits)
The mindful consumer: Balancing egoistic and altruistic motivations to purchase local food	Birch et al.	2018	local food
The interplay of past consumption, attitudes and personal norms in organic food buying	Koklic et al.	2019	organic food
The influence of Slovak consumer lifestyle on purchasing behaviour in the consumption of organic food	Janska et al.	2023	organic food
The influence of skepticism on the university Millennials' organic food product purchase intention	Hoyos-Vallejo et al.	2023	organic food

The Importance of Consumer Trust for the Emergence of a Market for Green Products: The Case of Organic Food	Nuttavuthisit and Thogersen	2017	organic food
The impacts of perceived moral obligation and sustainability self-identity on sustainability development: A theory of planned behavior purchase intention model of sustainability-labeled coffee and the moderating effect of climate change skepticism	Chen	2020	sustainability-labeled coffee
The Impact of Ecological Knowledge on Young Consumers' Attitudes and Behaviours towards the Food Market	Kuzniar et al.	2021	eco-friendly products
The impact of consumers' preferences for domestic food on dietary sustainability	Milford and Muiruru	2024	ready-made plant-based food
The effects of consumer consciousness, food safety concern and healthy lifestyle on attitudes toward eating "green"	Tan et al.	2022	green food

The Effect of Novel and Environmentally Friendly Foods on Consumer Attitude and Behavior: A Value-Attitude-Behavioral Model	Ma and Chang	2022	plant-based meat alternatives
The Determinants of Organic Vegetable Purchasing in Jabodetabek Region, Indonesia	Slamet et al.	2016	organic vegetables
The determinants of consumer behaviour of students from Brno when purchasing organic food	Svecova and Odehnalova	2019	organic food
The Defining Role of Environmental Self-Identity among Consumption Values and Behavioral Intention to Consume Organic Food	Qasim et al.	2019	organic food
Sustainable Seafood Consumption in Action: Relevant Behaviors and their Predictors	Richter et al.	2017	products with seafood label or seafood guide
Sustainable Seafood Consumption in Action: Relevant Behaviors and their Predictors (study 2)	Richter et al.	2017	products with seafood label or seafood guide
Sustainable packaging: Does eating organic really make a difference on product-packaging interaction?	Santos et al.	2021	organic products in sustainable packaging

Sustainable food consumption. Product choice or curtailment?	Verain et al.	2015	sustainable food consumption
Sustainable Food Consumption: Investigating Organic Meat Purchase Intention by Vietnamese Consumers	Nguyen et al.	2021	organic meat
Sustainable Consumption of Groceries: the Importance of Believing that One Can Contribute to Sustainable Development	Hanss et al.	2016	sustainable groceries
Sustainable consumption in organic food buying behavior: the case of quinoa	Nosi et al.	2020	organic quinoa-based products
Socio-environmental considerations and organic food consumption: An empirical investigation of the attitude of Indian consumers	Kirmani et al.	2022	organic food
Socio-demographics, implicit attitudes, explicit attitudes, and sustainable consumption in supermarket shopping	Panzone et al.	2016	sustainable food consumption
Social Feedback Loop in the Organic Food Purchase Decision-Making Process	Ogorevc et al.	2020	organic fruit and vegetables

Self-declared attitudes and beliefs regarding protein sources are a good prediction of the degree of transition to a low-meat diet in France	De Gavelle et al.	2019	meat
Role of consumer health consciousness, food safety & attitude on organic food purchase in emerging market: A serial mediation model	Nagaraj	2021	organic food
Results from Türkiye: Which Factors Drive Consumers to Buy Organic Food?	Bas et al	2024	organic food
Relationship between Personal Values and Intentions to Purchase Plant-Based Meat Alternatives: Application of the Dual Concern Theory	Jang and Cho	2022	plant-based meat alternatives (PBMA)
Relationship between adherence to the Mediterranean diet, sustainable and healthy eating behaviors, and climate change awareness: A cross-sectional study from Turkey	Metin et al.	2024	Mediterranean diet adherence

Relationship between adherence to the Mediterranean diet, sustainable and healthy eating behaviors, and awareness of reducing the ecological footprint	Kocaadam-Bozkurt and Bozkurt	2023	Mediterranean diet adherence
Reducing meat consumption in meat-loving Denmark: Exploring willingness, behavior, barriers and drivers	Hielkema and Lund	2021	meat
Purchasing Behavior of Organic Food among Chinese University Students	Ali et al.	2021	organic food
Purchase of organic vegetables as a form of pro-environmental behaviour: Application of Norm Activation Theory	Faletar et al.	2021	organic vegetables
Purchase intention toward organic food among young consumers using theory of planned behavior: role of environmental concerns and environmental awareness	Ahmed et al.	2021	organic food
Purchase intention of organic foods: are lifestyles of health and sustainability the reason for my purchase decision?	Kaur et al.	2023	organic food

Purchase intention of organic food under the influence of attributes, consumer trust and perceived value	Galindo Curvelo et al.	2019	organic food
Purchase Intention for Organic Food Products in Mexico: The Mediation of Consumer Desire	Leyva-Hernandez et al.	2021	organic food
Psychosocial drivers influencing local food purchasing: beyond availability, the importance of trust in farmers	Carfora and Catellani	2023	local food
Psychological consumer behavior and sustainable green food purchase	Mazhar et al.	2022	green food
Prospective “warm-glow” of reducing meat consumption in China: Emotional associations with intentions for meat consumption curtailment and consumption of meat substitutes	Taufik	2018	meat
Predictors of intention to reduce meat consumption due to environmental reasons- Results from Poland and Slovakia	Borusiak et al.	2022	meat
Predicting purchasing behavior of green food in Algerian context	Troudi and Bouyoucef	2020	green food

Predicting intentions to purchase organic food: the moderating effects of organic food prices	Liang	2016	organic food
Predicting and promoting the consumption of plant-based meat	Carfora et al.	2022	plant-based meat
Perceptions of Cultured Meat Among Youth and Messaging Strategies	Ruzgys and Pickering	2020	cultured meat
Perceptions and determinants of adopting sustainable eating behaviours among university students in Canada: a qualitative study using focus group discussions	Mollaei et al.	2023	healthy and sustainable food
Perceived value, trust and purchase intention of organic food: a study with Brazilian consumers	Watanabe et al.	2020	organic food
Perceived Value, Environmental Awareness and Intention to Purchase Meat with Carbon Neutral Meat Seal (CCN)	Campos et al.	2024	carbon neutral meat (CCN) certified meat
Palm oil: Understanding barriers to sustainable consumption	Sundaraja et al.	2021	sustainable palm-oil products

Other-regarding preferences in pro-environmental behaviours: Empirical analysis and policy implications of organic and local food products purchasing in Italy	Aprile and Fiorillo	2023	organic and local food
Organic Foods Purchase Behavior among Generation Y of Bangladesh: The Moderation Effect of Trust and Price Consciousness	Zheng et al.	2021	organic foods
Organic food purchases: does green trust play a part?	Rashid and Lone	2023	organic products
Organic Food Purchases in an Emerging Market: The Influence of Consumers' Personal Factors and Green Marketing Practices of Food Stores	Nguyen et al.	2029	organic meat
Organic food purchase decisions from a context-based behavioral reasoning approach	Nguyen and Dang	2022	organic food
Organic food preferences: A Comparison of American and Indian consumers	Boobalan et al.	2022	organic food

Organic food consumption in Taiwan: Motives, involvement, and purchase intention under the moderating role of uncertainty	Teng and Lu	2016	organic food
Organic Food Consumption in Italy: The Role of Subjective Relevance of Food as Mediator between Organic Food Choice Motivation and Frequency of Organic Food Consumption	Castellini et al.	2020	organic food
Organic food consumption in China: food safety concerns, perceptions, and purchase behavior under the moderating role of trust	Cao et al.	2023	organic food
Organic Food Consumption among Households in Hanoi: Importance of Situational Factors	Tran and Nguyen	2021	organic food
Organic food as self-presentation: The role of psychological motivation in older consumers' purchase intention of organic food	Hwang	2016	organic food

Organic food adoption motivations for sustainable consumption: moderating role of knowledge and perceived price	Khan et al.	2022	organic food
Non-vegan consumers buying vegan food: the moderating role of conformity	Martinelli and De Canio	2022	vegan food
Narrowing the gap: Factors driving organic food consumption	Chekima et al.	2017	organic food
Motivators and barriers to sustainable food consumption: Qualitative inquiry about organic food consumers in a developing nation	Yadav et al.	2019	organic food
Moral Foundations of Dietary Behavior and its Linkage to Sustainability and Feminism	Hackert et al.	2019	meat (vs vegi vs vegan)
Modelling the significance of health values, beliefs and norms on the intention to consume and the consumption of organic foods	Yang et al.	2023	organic food
Modelling Middle Class Consumers Purchase Intention towards Organic Food: An Insight from Indonesia	Najib et al.	2021	organic food

Mindfulness, Construction of Meaning, and Sustainable Food Consumption	Hunecke and Richter	2019	sustainable food consumption
Mediating Influences of Attitude on Internal and External Factors Influencing Consumers' Intention to Purchase Organic Foods in China	Chu	2018	organic food
Marketing and Socio- psychological Factors Influencing Organic Food Purchase and Post-Purchase Outcomes	Chauke and Duh	2019	organic food
Making More Sustainable Food Choices One Meal at a Time: Psychological and Practical Aspects of Meat Reduction and Substitution	Collier et al.	2022	plant-based meat alternatives (PBMA)
Is It All about the Price? An Analysis of the Purchase Intention for Organic Food in a Discount Setting by Means of Structural Equation Modeling	Katt and Meixner	2020	organic food
INVESTIGATION OF CONSUMERS 'ORGANIC FOOD PURCHASES IN THE CONTEXT OF THE RELATIONSHIP OF PERSONAL VALUES AND INDIVIDUAL FACTORS	Ercis et al.	2020	organic food

Investigating and stimulating sustainable dairy consumption behavior: An exploratory study in Vietnam	Hoang et al.	2023	sustainable dairy
Intentions to Consume Sustainably Produced Fish: The Moderator Effects of Involvement and Environmental Awareness	Skallerud et al.	2021	sustainably produced fish
Intention-behaviour gap and perceived behavioural control-behaviour gap in theory of planned behaviour: moderating roles of communication, satisfaction and trust in organic food consumption	Sultan et al.	2020	organic food
Intention to re-consume organic food: Sensory attributes, egoistic motive, and warm glow in the extended TPB	Cahyasita et al.	2021	organic food
Integrating the theory of planned behavior and the self-determination theory to promote Mediterranean diet adherence: A randomized controlled trial	Caso et al.	2024	Mediterranean diet adherence

Integrating the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Norm Activation Model to Investigate Organic Food Purchase Intention: Evidence from Vietnam	Le and Nguyen	2022	organic food
Intake of Animal-Based Foods and Consumer Behaviour towards Organic Food: The Case of Nepal	Budhathoki and Pandey	2021	organic food
Influences on purchase intentions of organic food consumers in an emerging economy	Dangi et al.	2020	organic food
Influences of background factors on consumers' purchase intention in China's organic food market: Assessing moderating role of word-of-mouth (WOM)	Li and Jaharuddin	2021	organic food
Influence of Customer Perceived Values on Organic Food Consumption Behaviour: Mediating Role of Green Purchase Intention	Kamboj and Kishor	2022	organic fruits & vegetables
Influence of Altruistic Motives on Organic Food Purchase: Theory of Planned Behavior	Boobalan et al.	2021	organic food

Individualistic or collectivistic: which consideration motivates purchasing intention of organic foods? A developing country perspective	Chowhury et al.	2023	organic food
Increasing organic food consumption: An integrating model of drivers and barriers	Hansmann et al.	2020	organic fruits & vegetables
Impacts of household norms and trust on organic food purchase behavior under adapted theory of planned behavior	Nguyen et al.	2023	organic food
Impact of trust and knowledge in the food chain on motivation-behavior gap in green consumption	Dong et al.	2022	green rice
Impact of consumption values on consumers' purchase of organic food and green environmental concerns	Suki et al.	2022	organic food
Identifying the key purchase factors for organic food among Chinese consumers	Li and Jaharuddin	2020	organic food
"I Eat Organic for My Benefit and Yours": Egoistic and Altruistic Considerations for Purchasing Organic Food and Their Implications for Advertising Strategists (study 1)	Kareklas et al.	2014	organic food

I did good, and we did bad: The impact of collective versus private emotions on pro-environmental food consumption	Onwezen	2015	organic food (meat, dairy, fruit, vegetables)
I did good, and we did bad: The impact of collective versus private emotions on pro-environmental food consumption (study 2)	Onwezen	2015	organic food (meat, dairy, fruit, vegetables)
I did good, and we did bad: The impact of collective versus private emotions on pro-environmental food consumption (study 3)	Onwezen	2015	organic food (meat, dairy, fruit, vegetables)
How the interplay between consumer motivations and values influences organic food identity and behavior	Hansen et al.	2018	organic food
How stable is the value basis for organic food consumption in China?	Thøgersen et al.	2016	organic vegetables
How perceived communication source and food value stimulate purchase intention of organic food: An examination of the stimulus-organism-response (SOR) model	Sultan et al.	2021	organic food

How health consciousness and social consciousness affect young consumers purchase intention towards organic foods	Su et al.	2022	organic food
How Green Consumption Value Affects Green Consumer Behaviour: The Mediating Role of Consumer Attitudes Towards Sustainable Food Logistics Practices	Alagarsamy et al.	2021	green food
How do values relate to the consumption of meat and dairy products and their plant-based alternatives?	Lehto et al.	2023	plant-based meat and dairy alternatives
How consumers' consciousness and perception levels affect purchase intention of organic chicken meat in Turkey	Bolat et al.	2020	organic chicken meat
How Collectivism Affects Organic Food Purchase Intention and Behavior: A Study with Norwegian and Portuguese Young Consumers	Roseira et al.	2022	organic food
Health-driven mechanism of organic food consumption: A structural equation modelling approach.	Wang et al.	2024	organic beef

Health Consciousness, Food Safety Concern, and Consumer Purchase Intentions Toward Organic Food: The Role of Consumer Involvement and Ecological Motives	Iqbal et al.	2021	organic food
Green Purchase Behaviour Gap: The Effect of Past Behaviour on Green Food Product Purchase Intentions among Individual Consumers	Witek and Kuzniar	2024	green food products
Green food purchasing behaviour: a multi- method approach of Generation Y in a developing country	Synodinos et al.	2023	organic food
Green Food Product Purchase Intention: Factors Influencing Malaysian Consumers	Yogananda and Nair	2019	green food products
Gen Z and sustainable diets: Application of The Transtheoretical Model and the theory of planned behaviour	Ruzgys and Pickerig	2024	sustainable food products
From pride to plate: how feelings of pride and guilt lead Gen Z to plant-based consumption at restaurants	Mahasuweeracha i et al.	2023	plant-based restaurant food

From Meatless Mondays to Meatless Sundays: Motivations for Meat Reduction among Vegetarians and Semi-vegetarians Who Mildly or Significantly Reduce Their Meat Intake	De Backer and Hudders	2014	meat
Food Innovation Adoption and Organic Food Consumerism-A Cross National Study between Malaysia and Hungary	Nathan et al.	2021	organic food
Fear of climate change consequences and predictors of intentions to alter meat consumption	Hunter and Rood	2016	meat
Fair trade food products: Insights about motivations for consumption behaviour in Italy	Verneau et al.	2016	fair trade products
Factors Influencing Organic Food Purchase Intention in Developing Countries and the Moderating Role of Knowledge	Wang et al.	2019	organic food
Factors influencing Indian consumers' actual buying behaviour towards organic food products	Singh and Verma	2017	organic food

Factors Influencing Consumers' Organic Food Continuous Purchase Intentions during the Post-Pandemic Era: An Empirical Investigation in China	Qi et al.	2023	organic food
Factors Influencing Consumers' Behaviour towards Purchasing Organic Foods: A Theoretical Model	Yilmaz	2023	organic food
Factors influencing consumers' behaviour towards organic food purchase in Denmark and Tanzania	Pacho and Batra	2021	organic food
Factors affecting purchase intention of organic food products: Evidence from a developing nation context	Bazhan et al.	2024	organic food
Factors affecting consumers' purchase intention of eco-friendly food in China: The evidence from respondents in Beijing	He et al.	2019	green food
Facilitators and inhibitors of organic food buying behavior	Tandon et al.	2021	organic food
Extending the theory of planned behaviour to predict sustainable food consumption	Arya et al.	2024	sustainable food

Extending the theory of planned behavior to understand consumer purchase behavior for organic vegetables in Brazil: The role of perceived health benefits, perceived sustainability benefits and perceived price	Dorce et al.	2021	organic vegetables
Exploring the role of consumer ethnocentrism in predicting the purchase intention for locally produced organic food in an emerging market	Chaturvedi et al.	2024	locally produced organic food
Exploring the Antecedents of Organic Food Purchase Intention: An Extension of the Theory of Planned Behavior	Tixeira et al.	2022	organic food
Exploring pro-environmental food purchasing behaviour: An empirical analysis of Italian consumers	Laureti and Benedetti	2018	organic food
Exploring Japanese Consumers' Motivators Related to Eating Soy Meat	Taki et al.	2023	soy meat

Exploring Influential Factors Including COVID-19 on Green Food Purchase Intentions and the Intention-Behaviour Gap: A Qualitative Study among Consumers in a Chinese Context	Qi et al.	2020	green food
Exploring Consumers' Purchase Intention of an Innovation of the Agri-Food Industry: A Case of Artificial Meat	Shen and Chen	2020	artificial meat (vegetarian burger)
Exploring consumers' behaviour towards short food supply chains	Giampietri et al.	2016	Short Food Supply Chain (SFSC) foods
Exploring consumer's perception and preferences towards purchase of non-certified organic food: A qualitative perspective	Mughal et al.	2021	non-certified organic food
Exploring attitude-behaviour inconsistencies in organic food consumption during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Klang Valley, Malaysia	Cheah and Aigbogun	2022	organic food
Exploration of seaweed consumption in Norway using the norm activation model: The moderator role of food innovativeness	Govaerts and Olsen	2022	food products containing seaweed

Explaining intention to reduce red and processed meat in the UK and Italy using the theory of planned behaviour, meat-eater identity, and the Transtheoretical model	Wolstenholme et al.	2021	red and processed meat
Examining the role of health consciousness, environmental awareness and intention on purchase of organic food: A moderated model of attitude	Parashar	2023	organic food
Examining the Factors That Affect Consumers' Purchase Intention of Organic Food Products in a Developing Country	Zayed et al.	2022	organic food
Examining consumer purchase intention towards organic food: An empirical study	Kamboj et al.	2023	organic food
Evaluation of adherence to the Mediterranean diet with sustainable nutrition knowledge and environmentally responsible food choices	Yassibas and Bolukbasi	2023	Mediterranean diet adherence
Evaluating the purchase behaviour of organic food by young consumers in an emerging market economy	Pham et al.	2019	organic food

Ethical food consumption drivers in Japan. A S-O-R framework application using PLS-SEM with a MGA assessment based on clustering	Morais et al.	2024	ethical food products
Ethical consumption intentions and choice behavior towards organic food. Moderation role of buying and environmental concerns	Kushwah et al.	2019	ethical food products
Environmental Consciousness and Organic Food Purchase Intention: A Moderated Mediation Model of Perceived Food Quality and Price Sensitivity	Wang et al.	2020	organic food
Environmental and Health Factors as Organic Fruit Purchase Drivers and the Mediating Role of Price and Effort	Llanos-Herrera et al.	2022	organic fruit
Enthusiastically consuming organic food An analysis of the online organic food purchasing behaviors of consumers with different food-related lifestyles	Rong-Da Liang	2014	organic food

Enabling sustainable plant-forward transition: European consumer attitudes and intention to buy hybrid products	Banovic et al.	2022	hybrid products
Employees buying organic food intention: An extension of the theory of planned behavior	Jiang and Wu	2022	organic food
Emotional or logical: reason for consumers to buy organic food products	Jose and Kuriakose	2021	organic fruits & vegetables
Elaborating on the attitude-behaviour gap regarding organic products: young Danish consumers and in-store food choice	Aschemann-Witzel and Aagaard	2014	organic food
Effects of University Students' Perceived Food Literacy on Ecological Eating Behavior towards Sustainability	Lee et al.	2022	ecological food consumption
EFFECTS OF ORGANIC FOOD PERCEIVED VALUES ON CONSUMERS' ATTITUDE AND BEHAVIOR IN DEVELOPING COUNTRY: MODERATING ROLE OF PRICE SENSITIVITY	Zinoubi	2021	organic food

EFFECT OF ORGANIC
FOOD-RELATED
LIFESTYLE TOWARDS
ATTITUDE AND
PURCHASE
INTENTION OF
ORGANIC FOOD:
EVIDENCE FROM
BRAZIL

Jungles et al.

2021

organic food

Eating novel foods: An
application of the
Theory of Planned
Behaviour to predict
the consumption of an
insect-based product

Menozzi et al.

2017

products containing
insect flour (e.g., a
cookie)

Eating like there's no
tomorrow: Public
awareness of the
environmental impact
of food and reluctance
to eat less meat as part
of a sustainable diet

Macdiarmid et al.

2016

meat

Eating green for health
or social benefits?
Interactions of attitudes
with self-identity on the
consumption of
vegetarian meals
among US and Chinese
college students

Zhang et al.

2021

vegetarian meal

Driving youngsters to
be green: The case of
plant-based food
consumption in
Indonesia

Suhartanto et al.

2022

plant-based food

Drivers of plant-based convenience foods consumption: Results of a multicomponent extension of the theory of planned behaviour	Contini et al.	2020	pre-cooked plant-based foods
Drivers of Organic Food Purchase Intention in a Developing Country: The Mediating Role of Trust	Ayyub et al.	2021	organic food
Drivers of local food consumption: a comparative study	Bianchi and Mortimer	2015	local food
Drivers of consumers' intention to adopt sustainable healthy dietary patterns: evidence from China	Chen et al.	2024	sustainable and healthy food
Does gender moderate the purchase intention of organic foods? Theory of reasoned action	Gundala et al.	2022	organic food
Do We Know Organic Food Consumers? The Personal and Social Determinants of Organic Food Consumption	Unal et al.	2019	organic food
Do normative triggers and motivations influence the intention to purchase organic food? An application of the goal-framing theory	Khan et al.	2023	organic food

Differentiating emotions in the theory of planned behaviour: evidence of improved prediction in relation to sustainable food consumerism	Martini et al.	2024	fair trade food products
Differentiating emotions in the theory of planned behaviour: evidence of improved prediction in relation to sustainable food consumerism (study 2)	Martini et al.	2024	food bought through SDG's
DEVELOPING A MODEL OF ORGANIC FOOD CHOICE BEHAVIOR	Suh et al.	2015	organic food
Determining Factors Affecting Consumer's Decision to Purchase Organic Chicken Meat	Kaygisiz et al.	2019	organic chicken meat
Determining consumers' intent to purchase organic foods in emerging market: price perception affect in moderated mediation model	Yilmazel	2023	organic food
DETERMINANTS OF THE THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR OF CONSUMER RELATED TO INTENTION TO PURCHASE OF ORGANIC VEGETABLES	dos Reis Neto et al.	2019	organic vegetables

Determinants of Organic Food Repurchase Intention from the Perspective of Brazilian Consumers	de Farias et al.	2019	organic food
Determinants of organic food purchasing intention: an empirical study of local consumers in Da Nang city, Central Vietnam	Mai et al.	2023	organic food
Determinants of organic food purchases: Evidence from household panel data	Janssen	2018	organic food
Determinants of organic food purchases intention: the application of an extended theory of planned behaviour	Imani et al.	2021	organic food
Determinants of organic food purchase intention: the moderating role of health consciousness	Devi et al.	2023	organic food
Determinants of Organic Food Consumption in Narrowing the Green Gap	Chekima et al.	2023	organic food
Determinants of Household Choice of Dairy and Plant-based Milk Alternatives: Evidence from a Field Survey	Boaitey and Minegishi	2020	dairy and plant-based milk

Determinants of healthy and sustainable food choices in parents with a higher and lower socioeconomic status: A qualitative study	Vos et al.	2022	sustainable and healthy food
Determinants and moderators of organic food purchase intention	Eberle et al.	2022	organic food
Determinant factors influencing organic food purchase intention and the moderating role of awareness: A comparative analysis	Asif et al.	2018	organic food
Decisional factors driving organic food consumption			
Generation of consumer purchase intentions	Teng and Wang	2015	organic food
Critical Factors Affecting Consumer Buying Behaviour of Organic Vegetables in Vietnam	Doan	2021	organic vegetables
Convenience food with environmentally-sustainable attributes: A consumer perspective	Stranieri et al.	2017	minimally-processed vegetables labelled with voluntary standards related to integrated agriculture
Consumption values, anxiety and organic food purchasing behaviour considering the moderating role of sustainable consumption attitude	Cao et al.	2022	organic food

Consumption of organic and functional food. A matter of well-being and health?	Goetzke et al.	2014	organic food
Consumers' willingness to buy and willingness to pay for fair trade food: The influence of consciousness for fair consumption, environmental concern, trust and innovativeness	Konuk	2019	fair-trade food
Consumers' sustainable food choices: Antecedents and motivational imbalance	Elhoushy	2020	sustainable food consumption
Consumers' purchase behavior in short food supply chains using social commerce in Indonesia	Sadeli et al.	2023	food from social commerce SFCS's
Consumers' perceptions of organic food attributes and cognitive and affective attitudes as determinants of their purchase intentions toward organic food	Lee and Yun	2015	organic food
Consumers' intention to adopt plant-based meat	Chen and Tsai	2023	plant-based meat
Consumers' beliefs, attitudes, and loyalty in purchasing organic foods The standard learning hierarchy approach	Lee and Goudeau	2014	organic food

Consumers' anti-consumption behavior toward organic food purchase: an analysis using SEM	Ashraf et al.	2019	organic food
Consumer purchasing behaviour of organic food in an emerging market	Le-Anh and Nguyen-To	2020	organic food
Consumer preferences toward organic food and the moderating role of knowledge: a case of Pakistan and Malaysia	Kashif et al.	2020	organic food
Consumer perceptions and attitudes of organic food products in Eastern China	Xie et al.	2015	organic food
Consumer motivations and desired product attributes for 2.0 plant-based products: a conceptual model of consumer insight for market-oriented product development and marketing.	Beacom et al.	2022	plant-based products
Consumer motivation for organic food consumption: Health consciousness or herd mentality	Wang et al.	2023	organic food
Consumer Intention to Buy Plant-Based Meat Alternatives: A Cross-Cultural Analysis	Bakr et al.	2023	plant-based meat alternatives (PBMA)

Consumer innovativeness and organic food adoption: The mediation effects of consumer knowledge and attitudes	Li et al.	2021	organic food
Consumer concerns over food insecurity drive reduction in the carbon footprint of food consumption	Righi et al.	2023	greenhouse gas emissions based on food consumption
Consumer buying motives and attitudes towards organic food in two emerging markets China and Brazil	Thogersen et al.	2015	Brazil: organic tomatoes. China: organic vegetables
Consumer attitudes and sociodemographic profiles in purchasing organic food products: evidence from a Greek and Swedish survey	Diagourtas et al.	2022	organic food
Consumer attitudes and buying behavior for green food products: From the aspect of green perceived value (GPV)	Woo and Kim	2019	green food
Consumer Attitude towards Organic Foods: A Multigroup Analysis across Genders	Yazar and Burucuoglu	2019	organic food
Climate Change and Consumer's Attitude toward Insect Food	Chang et al.	2019	insect food

CHINESE
CONSUMERS'
PURCHASE
INTENTION FOR
ORGANIC MEAT: AN
EXTENSION OF THE
THEORY OF
PLANNED
BEHAVIOUR

Bhutto et al.

2022

organic meat

Causal complexity of
sustainable
consumption:
Unveiling the equifinal
causes of purchase
intentions of plant-
based meat alternatives

Bhattacharyya et
al.

2023

plant-based meat
alternatives (PBMA)

Can Unveiling the
Relationship between
Nutritional Literacy
and Sustainable Eating
Behaviors Survive Our
Future?

Mortas et al.

2023

sustainable and
healthy food

Can Consumers Do It
All? An Exploration of
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Sustainable Palm Oil
Products

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sustainable palm-oil
products

Buying Organic Food
Products: The Role of
Trust in the Theory of
Planned Behavior

Canova et al.

2020

organic food

Buying Organic Food
Products: The Role of
Trust in the Theory of
Planned Behavior

Canova et al.

2020

organic fruits and
vegetables

(study 2)

Buying Behaviour towards Eco-Labelled Food Products: Mediation Moderation Analysis	Alam et al.	2023	eco-labelled food products
Boosting ecological food consumption behavior among millennials: role of health consciousness, perceived consumer effectiveness and ethical self-identity	Amin and Tarun	2022	ecological food products
BELIEFS ABOUT EFFECTS OF ORGANIC PRODUCTS AND THEIR IMPACT ON INTENTION TO PURCHASE ORGANIC FOOD	Ham	2019	organic food
Beliefs underlying older adults? intention to consume plant-based protein foods: A qualitative study	Drolet-Labelle et al.	2023	plant-based
Beggars can't be choosers: factors influencing intention to purchase organic food in pandemic with the moderating role of perceived barriers	Rehman et al.	2023	organic food

<p>'Nobody cares about the environment': Kyrgyz' perspectives on enhancing environmental sustainable consumption practices when facing limited sustainability awareness</p> <p>A behavioural reasoning perspective on the consumption of local food. A study on REKO, a social media-based local food distribution system</p>	<p>Jarkyn Shadymanova, Stefan Wahlen, Hilje van der Horst</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>sustainable food consumption</p>
<p>A comparison of influencing factors on attitudes towards plant-based, insect-based and cultured meat alternatives in Germany</p>	<p>Kumar et al.</p>	<p>2021</p>	<p>local food</p>
<p>"A healthy outside starts from the inside": A matter of sustainable consumption behavior in Italy and Pakistan</p> <p>A moderated mediation study of consumer extrinsic motivation and CSR beliefs towards organic drinking products in an emerging economy</p>	<p>Heijnk et al.</p>	<p>2023</p>	<p>Plant-based foods, insect-based foods, cultured meat alternatives</p>
<p>Ishaq et al.</p>	<p>2021</p>	<p>organic food</p>	
<p>Dang et al.</p>	<p>2021</p>	<p>organic drinking products</p>	

A Novel Model to Predict Plant-Based Food Choice-Empirical Study in Southern Vietnam	Nguyen et al.	2020	plant-based foods
A qualitative study of young peoples' thoughts and attitudes to follow a more plant-based diet	McInnes et al.	2023	plant-based foods
A revisit to the role of gender, age, subjective and objective knowledge in consumers' attitudes towards organic food	Fatha & Ayoubi	2021	organic food
A Steak for Supper if the Cow Did Not Suffer: Understanding the Mechanisms Behind People's Intention to Purchase Animal Welfare-Friendly (AWF) Meat Products	Beldad & Hegner	2020	AWF (animal-welfare products)
A Survey of Consumer Perceptions of Plant-Based and Clean Meat in the USA, India, and China	Bryant et al.	2019	Clean meat, plant-based meat
A values-beliefs-attitude model of local food consumption: An empirical study in China and Denmark	Zhang et al.	2020	Local food

<p>Above and beyond meat: the role of consumers' dietary behavior for the purchase of plant-based food substitutes</p>	<p>Kopplin & Rausch</p>	<p>2022</p>	<p>plant-based food substitutes</p>
<p>Affective explicit and implicit attitudes towards vegetarian and vegan food consumption: The role of mindfulness</p>	<p>Siebertz et al.</p>	<p>2022</p>	<p>meat-based vs. vegetarian foods</p>
<p>Altruistic or egoistic: Which value promotes organic food consumption among young consumers? A study in the context of a developing nation</p>	<p>Yadav</p>	<p>2016</p>	<p>organic food</p>
<p>An analysis of factors affecting selection of organic food: Perception of consumers in China regarding weak signals</p>	<p>Liu et al.</p>	<p>2021</p>	<p>organic food</p>
<p>An analysis of purchase intentions toward organic food on health consciousness and food safety with/under structural equation modeling</p>	<p>Hsu et al.</p>	<p>2016</p>	<p>organic food</p>
<p>An integrated framework to explain consumers' purchase intentions toward green food in the Chinese context</p>	<p>Qi & Ploeger</p>	<p>2021</p>	<p>green food</p>

An Investigation of Meat Eating in Samples from Australia and Germany: The Role of Justifications, Perceptions, and Empathy	Northrope et al.	2024	meat
Analyzing organic food purchase intentions: eco-literacy and innovation resistance	Bhutto & Rutelione	2024	organic food
Antecedents of Consumers' Intention and Behavior to Purchase Organic Food in the Portuguese Context	Ferreira & Pereira	2023	organic food
Antecedents of Organic Food Products Intention and Behaviors: Evidence from Vietnam	Pham	2020	organic food
Antecedents of Purchase Intention toward Organic Food in an Asian Emerging Market: A Study of Urban Vietnamese Consumers	Nguyen et al.	2019	organic food
Application of consumer style inventory (CSI) to predict young Indian consumer's intention to purchase organic food products	Prakash et al.	2018	organic food

Application of the Theory of Planned Behaviour to predict Iranian students' intention to purchase organic food	Yazdanpanah & Forouzani	2015	organic food
Applying an Extended Theory of Planned Behavior to Sustainable Food Consumption	Alam et al.	2020	sustainable food
Applying the theory of behavioral choice to plant-based dietary intentions.	Gifford et al.	2024	plant-based food
Applying the theory of reasoned action to examine consumers' attitude and willingness to purchase organic foods	Kumar et al.	2023	organic food
Are green consumers really green? Exploring the factors behind the actual consumption of organic food products	Testa et al.	2019	organic food
Assessing Urban Consumer Intention on Purchasing of Organic Food in Sri Lanka	Wijesinghe & Aththanayaka	2021	organic food
Assessment of millennial organic food consumption and moderating role of food neophobia in Pakistan	Kashif et al.	2023	organic food

Assessment of the impacts of the consumers' awareness of organic food on consumption behavior	Demirtas	2019	organic food
Associations of food motives with red meat and legume consumption in the population-based DILGOM study	Hentila et al.	2023	legumes